

Innovation in Future Internet Scenario with Network Programmability and Smart Systems

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Abstract

This "presentation paper" discusses the innovation scenario with Software-defined Networking (SDN)/OpenFlow for smart systems. A "presentation paper" format is used with slides and bibliographic references to subsidize and enrich contents lecture. This talk was presented at Campus Party - BA - Brazil 2017.

Index Terms

Future Internet, Software-defined Networking, OpenFlow, Cognitive Management, Resource Allocation, Bandwidth Allocation Model, Case-based Reasoning, Reinforcement Learning, CBR, RL, GBAM.

1 INTRODUCTION

As discussed in [1], "the current scenario of communication networks, such as 5G, Cloud, IoT, vehicular and MPLS networks, is marked by a wide variety and large distribution of services, applications and users alongside with a high volume of data exchanges with heterogeneous quality assurance requirements (SLA, QoE, QoS)".

Actual evolution of computer networks is being fostered by different factors and aspects like:

- The continuous Internet/web growing, diversity and complexity;
- Network requirements becoming highly diversified, ranging from miniaturized interconnect RFID tags and IoT sensor applications to large complex server farms; and
- Users demanding more intelligent, easy to use (ubiquitous) and pervasive applications.

Researchers and developers are investigating and developing brand new technical approaches in terms of network architecture, protocols and intelligent tools to better support this new network scenario.

Considering this evolutionary trend, this talk focus on elaborating about some fundamental aspects of current network architecture and exploring new networking paradigms (SDN) and technological alternatives (Cognitive Management with Artificial Intelligence) to support the new requirements and evolution of actual networks.

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 - *Invited Professor at HTW - Hochschule für Technik und Wirtschaft des Saarlandes, Saarbrücken - Germany.*
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2 TALK

Innovation in Future Internet Scenario with Network Programmability and Smart Systems

Inovação na Internet do Futuro com “Programabilidade” de Redes & Sistemas Inteligentes

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Programa de Pós Graduação em Sistemas de Computação

Fig. 1.

- > Papers to read:
- > Complementary papers:
- > Books:
- > Manuals and references:

What INNOVATION means & What are the opportunities with FUTURE INTERNET

INNOVATION & FUTURE INTERNET

Fig. 2.

- > Papers to read: [2]
- > Complementary papers:
- > Books:
- > Manuals and references:

INNOVATION

(just a refresh)

- ◆ Briefly: new idea(s) aggregating value to a product
 - Innovation should lead to high return (charging value, reducing production cost or both)

- ◆ “Objectively” for this talk:
 - To explore ideas and solutions focusing on:
 - ◆ Technological opportunities
 - ◆ Large scale market
 - ◆ User demands and requirements

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Fig. 3.

- > Papers to read:
- > Complementary papers:
- > Books:
- > Manuals and references:

Innovation & Future Internet

◆ What really “FUTURE INTERNET” means?

- Global geographical scope and connectivity
- Big numbers
- Heterogeneous networks and appliances
- Highly ubiquitous

Fig. 4.

- > Papers to read:
- > Complementary papers:
- > Books: [3]
- > Manuals and references:

Talk Focus

◆ A network of networks (network view)

◆ The web (user view)

Innovation: SDN in this scenario + Innovation: intelligence in this scenario

What is behind the Internet (RE)Evolution?

Fig. 5.

- > Papers to read: [4]
- > Complementary papers: [5]
- > Books:
- > Manuals and references:

Future Internet “Users and Applications”

- ◆ A huge number of highly interesting applications, demanded by billions of users with variable requirements in relation to the INTERNET

Fig. 6.

- > Papers to read: [6]
- > Complementary papers:
- > Books:
- > Manuals and references:

Internet (Re)Evolution

Global Users

◆ Big number for “Internet users”

◆ Future Internet “users”:

- Global “users”: computers, smartphones, cars, drones, home appliances, “things”, sensors and “people”

Fig. 7.

- > Papers to read:
- > Complementary papers:
- > Books:
- > Manuals and references:

Future Internet

Actual Technological Cycle and “Content”

◆ Future Internet: actual stuff + **mobile internet + wearable + IoT (Internet of Things) + ...**

◆ Basic trends:

- High volume of data
- Multimedia content with increasing quality, easy access and high volume
- User-centric approaches (especially to **INNOVATE**)

Fig. 8.

- > Papers to read:
- > Complementary papers:
- > Books:
- > Manuals and references:

Future Internet

High Volume of “Content” is a trend

◆ **Data & “Content”** (documents, pictures, tweets, messages, ...):

- Digital information by 2011: ± 2 Zettabytes (findable, sharable, ...)*
- Up 09 times in 05 years
- Still going up → continuous trend

01 zettabyte = 01 Trillion Gigabytes - 10²¹

* Source: IDC Report “Extracting Value from Chaos”

Fig. 9.

- > Papers to read:
- > Complementary papers:
- > Books:
- > Manuals and references:

Internet & Future Internet

An easy view of Big Data Scenario

Internet Scenario

Future Internet Scenario

◆ **High volume of data, tagged, findable, shared, ...**

- High quality photos taken with increasingly lower cost cameras (+smartphone) and possibly stored in a scalable low cost memory system (cloud, social networks, ...) and need to be findable, tagged and shared.
- + Selfies

Fig. 10.

- > Papers to read:
- > Complementary papers:
- > Books:
- > Manuals and references:

Wearable, Appliances, “Things”, Sensors, Flyable, ... Trends

- ◆ “Wearable” are present in domains such as entertainment, e-health, ...
- ◆ “Appliances” (TV, sound, refrigerator, mobile, ...) are present in domains such as home entertainment and smart-home
- ◆ “Internet of Things - IoT” with “sensors”:
 - 100 billion sensors by 2020
 - “Cloud” support is a trend
- ◆ **Development & Research:** typically multidisciplinary in broad domains like smart-cities, smart-grid, e-agriculture, smart-water, environment management, green computing, intelligent transportation systems, ...

Fig. 11.

- > Papers to read:
- > Complementary papers:
- > Books:
- > Manuals and references:

Talk Focus

◆ A network of networks (network view)

◆ The web (user view)

↓ **Networking**

↓ **Data Analytics**

Innovation: SDN in this scenario + Innovation: intelligence in this scenario

What is behind the Internet (RE)Evolution? →

Fig. 12.

- > Papers to read:
- > Complementary papers:
- > Books:
- > Manuals and references:

Internet Evolution (so far)

- ◆ Wide scale proliferation and service diversification has lead to:
 - “Plumbing” of IP external artifacts:
 - ◆ IPv6, NAT, CIDR, DiffServ, MPLS, Mobile IP, ...
- ◆ Overall result:
 - Conflict with Internet (IP) basic principles and assumptions
 - Current network becomes inefficient, difficult to manage and with various “side effects”
 - IP architecture “ossification”

→ More difficult to innovate

Fig. 13.

- > Papers to read:
- > Complementary papers:
- > Books:
- > Manuals and references:

Incremental Network Evolution

IP Developments (examples)

- ◆ Subnets, Autonomous Systems (AS) and DNS (Domain Name System)
- ◆ CIDR – *Classless InterDomain Routing*
- ◆ TCP Congestion Control
- ◆ IP Multicast
- ◆ IPv6
- ◆ NAT – *Network Address Translation*
- ◆ IPSec – *IP Security*
- ◆ Mobile IP
- ◆ Quality of Service (QoS) and Diffserv (Differentiated Services)
- ◆ Caches
- ◆ Firewalls
- ◆ Other ...

→ **Too many patches!!!**

Fig. 14.

- > Papers to read:
- > Complementary papers:
- > Books:
- > Manuals and references:

Fig. 15.

- > Papers to read:
- > Complementary papers:
- > Books: [7] [8]
- > Manuals and references:

SDN Network Programmability

◆ SDN programmability view

Fig. 16.

- > Papers to read: [9] [10]
- > Complementary papers: [11]
- > Books:
- > Manuals and references:

Classical/ Typical Application Programming (TCP/IP-based)

Applications are “network users”

- No application direct interference on network operation
- Network controlled by Network Management/ OAM (Operation Administration and Management)

Fig. 17.

- > Papers to read: [12]
- > Complementary papers:
- > Books:
- > Manuals and references:

SDN Applications & Network Programming

- What is added?
- Is SDN disruptive?

Fig. 18.

- > Papers to read:
- > Complementary papers: [13]
- > Books:
- > Manuals and references:

How SDN does this?

◆ OpenFlow-based approach

Fig. 19.

- > Papers to read: [9] [12]
- > Complementary papers: [14]
- > Books:
- > Manuals and references:

SDN Programmability

Source: Software-Defined Networking: A Comprehensive Survey, Diego Kreutz et al, May, 2014

- ◆ Flow-based processing
- ◆ **Packet forwarding decisions are based on “flow matches”**
- ◆ Forwarding equipment (Switch/Router) has a “flow forwarding table”
- ◆ Forwarding table defines “flows and flow actions”:
 - **Defined/ programmed by a “controller” using the “OpenFlow protocol”**
- ◆ Secure control channel (SSL – Secure Sockets Layer) between the controller and the SDN-capable equipment

Fig. 20.

- > Papers to read:
- > Complementary papers:
- > Books:
- > Manuals and references:

OpenFlow Applications

Innovation on “USER APPLICATIONS”

- ◆ MMOG Massively Multiplayer On-Line Games/ Games
- ◆ User-centric forwarding
 - Forwarding/ routing based on “user” information
- ◆ Data-centric forwarding and Content-based routing
 - Forwarding/ routing based on “raw data” and “content”
- ◆ Context-based
 - Forward/ routing based on “context”
- ◆ IoT/ sensors data collection, aggregation and forwarding
- ◆ Security applications
- ◆ OpenFlow is applicable to cloud, wireless networks, optical networks, sensor networks, IoT networks, access networks, other
 - May deal with network heterogeneity
- ◆ Other

- User demands and needs
- Future Internet context
- **Potential Innovation**

See Stanford videos at <http://www.openflow.org/videos/>

Fig. 21.

- > Papers to read:
- > Complementary papers:
- > Books:
- > Manuals and references:

Other Possible SDN Estrategies for **Innovation**

1. **Innovation** on the network equipment's (boxes)

- All-in-one SDN-capable equipment
- Unified view of equipment (basic dummy switch implements all network functions – forwarding, routing, access point, firewall, ...)

Fig. 22.

- > Papers to read: [15] [16]
- > Complementary papers: [17]
- > Books:
- > Manuals and references:

Other Possible SDN Estrategies for **Innovation**

2. **Innovation** on network infrastructure operation

- In this case SDN/OpenFlow is used mimicking TCP/IP operation (it is preserved typically for backward compatibility)
- The direct control of the equipment is used to optimize operation:
 - ◆ Traffic Engineering and path control, Routing, Resource Allocation, other
 - ◆ Security
- Optimizations on the network infrastructure (**Google did it**)
- Domain of corporate networks (ISPs, telecom operators, big networks, ...)

Google experience with SDN/OpenFlow: **OpenFlow@Google** – Available at https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Joberto_Martins - Campus Party BA Talk 2017

Fig. 23.

- > Papers to read: [6]
- > Complementary papers:
- > Books:
- > Manuals and references:

Limitations

- ◆ Actually applicable on networks in which we have “control”
 - Any type of network or corporate network in which you “manage” the infrastructure
- ◆ New technology with few programming tools and support
- ◆ Possible at Internet but needs large consensus of big players (ISPs, Telecom operators, others)

Fig. 24.

- > Papers to read: [18] [19] [16]
- > Complementary papers:
- > Books: [20]
- > Manuals and references:

Talk Focus

◆ A network of networks (network view)

◆ The web (user view)

↓ **Data Analytics**

Innovation: SDN in this scenario + Innovation: intelligence in this scenario

What is behind the Internet (RE)Evolution? →

Fig. 25.

- > Papers to read:
- > Complementary papers:
- > Books:
- > Manuals and references:

Why and How should we Innovate adding some “Intelligence” to Applications

Why?

- ◆ Future Internet scenarios and requirements:
 - Huge volume of data (Big Data)
 - ◆ Needs some “clever mining”
 - Context-based solutions
 - User-centric solutions
 - Data-centric solutions
 - Users do expect “ubiquitous” applications
 - ◆ More intelligent systems will take some decisions and will behave more ubiquitously
 - ◆ More “transparent” applications

Fig. 27.

- > Papers to read: [21]
- > Complementary papers:
- > Books:
- > Manuals and references:

Why and **How** should we Innovate adding some Intelligence to Applications **HOW**

- ◆ Autonomic computing
- ◆ Data analytics

} **Focus of this talk**

◆ Various approaches and techniques:

- Autonomy
- Machine Learning
- Case Based Reasoning (CBR)
- Reinforced Learning (RL)
- Deep Learning
- Fuzzy Logic
- Other approaches

Fig. 28.

- > Papers to read:
- > Complementary papers:
- > Books:
- > Manuals and references:

Innovation with Autonomy

◆ Autonomic behavior:

- Self-configuration, self-optimization, self-healing, ...
- Knowledge Plan:
 - ◆ Machine Learning
 - ◆ CBR - Case-Based Reasoning
 - ◆ RL – Reinforced Learning
 - ◆ Fuzzy logic
 - ◆ Others
- Trend for Future Internet applications

Reference: "Architectures for the Future Networks and Next Generation Internet: a Survey
Subharti Paul, Jianli Pan and Raj Jain, Computer Communications, 2011

Fig. 29.

- > Papers to read: [21] [1] [22]
- > Complementary papers: [23]
- > Books:
- > Manuals and references:

Resource Allocation & Autonomy

- ◆ Knowledge plan:
 - CBR – Case Based Reasoning
 - Other approaches can be implemented

Fig. 30.

- > Papers to read: [24] [21]
- > Complementary papers: []
- > Books: [25] [26] [27]
- > Manuals and references: []

Autonomy

Knowledge Plan with CBR (Case Based Reasoning)

4R

Fig. 31.

- > Papers to read: [28] [29]
- > Complementary papers: [22]
- > Books:
- > Manuals and references:

Resource Allocation & Autonomy with SDN/ OpenFlow

Fig. 32.

- > Papers to read: [30]
- > Complementary papers:
- > Books: [26]
- > Manuals and references:

World Cities - Numbers

- ◆ People migration to cities:
 - 1800: 3% of population lived in cities
 - 2040 – World: 65%
 - 2040 – Europe: 80%
- ◆ 30 cities with more than 10 million inhabitants by 2014
- ◆ Largest cities in the world:
 - Consume 85% of world's energy
 - Produce 80% of the waste

→ Problem

Source: "On Computational Infrastructure Requirements to Smart and Autonomic Cities Framework"

Available at:

--- Research Gate (Joberto Martins): https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Joberto_Martins

--- Academia (Joberto Martins): <https://unifacs.academia.edu/JobertoMartins>

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Fig. 34.

- > Papers to read: [31]
- > Complementary papers:
- > Books:
- > Manuals and references:

Some (not all) Perceivable Problems in Cities

Fig. 35.

- > Papers to read: [32]
- > Complementary papers: [33]
- > Books:
- > Manuals and references:

Smart City – Drafting the Idea

◆ Basic requirements to get to a “Smart City”:

- Infrastructure (networks, devices/ “things”, ...)
- Process (technical and managerial)
- People engaged
- **Innovation:**
 - ◆ **Everybody can contribute**
 - ◆ **Opportunity for Brazil and you**
 - ◆ **Strategic approach worldwide (extremely strong in Asia and Europe)**

Fig. 36.

- > Papers to read: [34]
- > Complementary papers:
- > Books:
- > Manuals and references:

Smart City – Application Areas & Innovation

- ◆ Smart Home
- ◆ Smart Living
- ◆ Smart Building
- ◆ Smart Grid
- ◆ E-government
- ◆ Smart Traffic
- ◆ Smart Street
- ◆ Smart Parking
- ◆ Smart Transportation
- ◆ Smart Health (e-health)
- ◆ Smart Security
- ◆ Smart Infrastructure
- ◆ Urban planning and management assisted by technology
- ◆ Smart Environment
- ◆ Smart Government
- ◆ Smart Mobility
- ◆ Smart Public Services
- ◆ Smart Economy
- ◆ Smart Waste Management (recycling of waste, residual management, recovery of waste organics & energy)
- ◆ Smart Education (e-Education)
- ◆ Other

Smart City = Smart-*

Fig. 37.

- > Papers to read:
- > Complementary papers:
- > Books:
- > Manuals and references:

Smart City – Smart Home Applications & Equipment

- ◆ Appliances control:
 - Internet Indoor (TVs – WIFI – Computers – Games)
 - Home Theater
 - Access control
 - Video cameras
 - Media control
 - Automation
 - Online games – MMOGs – Massively Multiplayer On-Line Games

- ◆ Home gateway:
 - Among appliances and among networks

- ◆ Energy-efficient home

◆

Technical Aspects of Smart City Projects? ➔

Fig. 38.

- > Papers to read:
- > Complementary papers:
- > Books:
- > Manuals and references:

Smart City & Communications

◆ Communications are necessary on Smart City projects:

- Human-to-Human (H2H) communications, Machine-to-Machine (M2M) communications, Human-to-Machine (H2M) communications
- Smart City requirements with Future Internet (FI):
 - ◆ Large volume of data
 - ◆ Highly distributed
 - ◆ Highly heterogeneous technologies
 - ◆ Ubiquity
 - Computers are there but we, fundamentally, do not perceive
 - "Cars" is a good example

→ IoT, mobile and mobility do fit in?

Fig. 39.

- > Papers to read: [35]
- > Complementary papers:
- > Books:
- > Manuals and references:

Smart City

Components of a Project (typical)

Fig. 40.

- > Papers to read: [36]
- > Complementary papers: [37]
- > Books:
- > Manuals and references:

Smart City & Big Data

- ◆ Aspects of the “**big data**” issue:
 - Large volume of collected/ gathered data (distributed)
 - Requires large and low cost storage
 - Requires ontologies:
 - ◆ How systems interoperate among themselves and among various physical components (sensors, actuators, ...)
 - Requires aggregation
 - Geo-referencing (GIS – Geographical Information Systems approach) might be associated to the collected data
 - Statistics and analytics
 - Data sharing
 - Decision-support systems (+intelligence)

Fig. 41.

- > Papers to read: [36]
- > Complementary papers:
- > Books:
- > Manuals and references:

Smart City – Smart Building Technology & Projects

Smart Building

- Energy Optimization
- Asset Management
- Facility Management
- Video Surveillance
- Recycling and Power Generation
- Automatic Fault Detection Diagnosis
- Supervisory Control
- Audio / Video Distribution Management

Fig. 42.

- > Papers to read: [38] [39] [40]
- > Complementary papers: [41]
- > Books:
- > Manuals and references:

Smart City – Smart Transportation Technology & Projects

Smart Transportation

- Intelligent Transportation
- Smart Public Transportation
- Integrated Fare Management
- Fleet Optimization
- Tolling Solutions
- Real-time Adaptive Traffic Management
- Smart Parking
- Traveler Information Systems

CONNECTED VEHICLES ITS – Intelligent Transportation Systems

Fig. 43.

- > Papers to read:
- > Complementary papers:
- > Books:
- > Manuals and references:

Smart City Projects around the World

◆ Smart City projects in Europe:

- Barcelona, Helsinki, Santander, Amsterdam, Copenhagen, Paris, Vienna, Eindhoven, Stockholm, London, Hamburg, Berlin, Singapore, San Petersburg, Guadalajara

PARIS:

- The city has more than 20,000 bikes (**VeloLib**) for sharing.
- 5% reduction in vehicle congestion in the city.
- The city has one of the world's first and most expensive EV car sharing programs.
 - **Autolib** with 3,000 EVs in its car sharing fleet.
- Paris' ecosystem is rated 11th best in the world.

BARCELONA:

- Bike-sharing project with more than 6,000 bikes.
- Uses various sensors from noise and air contamination to traffic congestion and waste management.
- The life expectancy in Barcelona is among the highest of cities (approx 83 years).

Source: A report prepared by **Boyd Cohen**, Ph.D., LEED AP, is a climate strategist helping to lead communities, cities and companies on the journey towards the low carbon economy. Dr. Cohen is the co-author of *Climate Capitalism: Capitalism in the Age of Climate Change* January 13, 2014

Fig. 44.

- > Papers to read: [42]
- > Complementary papers:
- > Books:
- > Manuals and references:

IFBA – UNIFACS Smart City Research Project Example

◆ SACi – Smart and Autonomic Cities

- Romildo Martins (in Memoria), Alan Freitas, Flavia Maristela and Joberto Martins
- Framework
- Smart Health
- Smart Grid
- Smart Environment
- Smart Street

Source: “On Computational Infrastructure Requirements to Smart and Autonomic Cities Framework” Available at:

- Research Gate (Joberto Martins): https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Joberto_Martins
- Academia (Joberto Martins): <https://unifacs.academia.edu/JobertoMartins>

Fig. 45.

- > Papers to read: [43] [44]
- > Complementary papers:
- > Books:
- > Manuals and references:

IFBA – UNIFACS Smart City Research Project

◆ Smart Health:

- Remote monitoring of citizens
- WHMS4 – Wearable Health monitoring and Scalable Secure System
 - ◆ Set of sensors and devices on clothing (wearable)
- Focus: elderly people, facilitate medical support logistics, other

◆ Smart Grid:

- Smart Grid Management System
- Focus: to treat power network reconfiguration and to improves load balancing on cities

◆ Smart Environment:

- Environment Management System
- Focus: air quality, water quality and quality in urban spaces

◆ Smart Street:

- Lamppost as smart device
- Focus: transport and mobile information, quality of live, public lighting control, other

Fig. 46.

- > Papers to read: [36]
- > Complementary papers:
- > Books:
- > Manuals and references:

Innovation & SDN & Intelligence at UNIFACS

- ◆ **PPGCOMP** – Masters Program on Computer Science:
 - Masters, IC (Iniciação Científica) and TCC
 - <http://www.unifacs.br/mestrado/mestrado-em-sistemas-e-computacao/>
- ◆ **ADMComp** – PhD in Administration/ Computer Science focused on System Innovation (*being created*)
- ◆ **PPDRU**: IoT and Urban Planning (PhD and MsC programs)

Programa de Pós Graduação em
Sistemas de Computação

PPGCOMP

Fig. 47.

- > Papers to read:
- > Complementary papers:
- > Books:
- > Manuals and references:

Thanks

Discussion and Questions

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Slides available at:

--- JSMNet (Joberto's site): <https://jobertomartins.com/>

--- RG: https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Joberto_Martins

--- Academia: <https://unifacs.academia.edu/JobertoMartins>

Fig. 48.

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